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Patent Title: **STM-Strategic Tourism Management: Strategic Workflow in Hospitality and Tourism Management**

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Complete Specification: **Australian Government.**

TITLE OF THE INVENTION

STM-Strategic Tourism Management: Strategic Workflow in Hospitality and Tourism Management

FIELD OF THE INVENTION

The present invention relates to hospitality and tourism industries, in particular it relates to a kind of strategic workflow in tourism management.

BACKGROUND OF THE INVENTION

The present invention solves many problems by providing a system and method for customizing hospitality and tourism services within a hospitality site. Offering several practical applications in the technical arts, the present invention reduces lengthy check-in procedures, increases the flexibility of a hospitality site's current amenities, and allows hospitality sites to offer additional customized amenities. The present invention accomplishes the above with little or no additional staffing. Along with progress and the development of science and technology, tourism is increasingly becoming the important selection that people have a holiday, and the sight spot of hot topic is often It is the first-selections gone on a journey of people, when scenic spot number is more, As the world economy grows and international tourism rapidly expands, there has been a recent explosion in the celebrity tour business where many tours take celebrity seekers to visit residences owned and hotspots frequented by celebrities past and present. Celebrity-oriented van and bus tours trade on the ever-growing interests in the private lives of celebrities and the fantasies of serendipitous celebrity encounters. In places like Hollywood, Beverly Hills, and New York City, visitors pay a hefty fee for roofless bus tours that last for only an hour or two, gawking at the luxuriousness of celebrity estates and trying to catch stars living or working in their natural surroundings. To this end, a gateway or firewall controlling access between the local area network (LAN) of the hotel and the Internet includes a default rule that causes unauthorized guest devices to display the login portal in the web browser.

SUMMARY OF THE INVENTION

The hotel industry has long been viewed as a customer-service industry in addition to its primary objective of "providing a bed for the night." In fact, some hotels have developed outstanding accommodations that are commonly used as convention centers and reception halls rather than

temporary living quarters. To distinguish the difference in accommodations and services a guest can expect from a particular hotel, the one-to-five-star rating system, an internationally recognized business practice, is applied. The British Tourist Authority has the following to say about star ratings: "star ratings symbolize the level of service, range of facilities, and quality of guest care that you can expect. Hotels are required to meet progressively higher standards as they move up the scale from one to five stars." A hotel with a one-star rating offers practical accommodation with a limited range of facilities and services, but a high standard of cleanliness throughout and 80 percent of bedrooms will have private bathroom facilities. A five star hotel offers the highest international quality of accommodation, facilities, services and cuisine. There will be a range of extra facilities to make the patron feel well cared for by professional, attentive staff who provide flawless guest services.

Presently, most five-star hotels employ some form of computerized property-management system to enable them to track a guest's stay duration, pay-per-view ordering, room-service ordering, smoking/nonsmoking room request, etc. Current property-management systems offer a marginal benefit to the hotels that employ them beyond tracking account activity. In addition, they offer virtually no added value to the hotel guest. A limited number of guest preferences such as smoking/nonsmoking rooms are indicated during booking of the room or at check-in, but no mechanism exists, save the present invention, to keep track of guest preferences and to make these preferences known to various associated hotels. Thus, a hotel in southern Florida does not follow or learn about preferences from guests who stay in western Missouri.

The prior art results in a great deal of time wasted by the guest and hotel staff continually traversing the same process during room booking and check-in. A new system is needed to streamline the process to reduce wasted effort and provide a greater variety of customized services. For example, it is common for hotels to provide guests with complimentary copies of national newspapers. However, no mechanism currently exists for a hotel to know the dates of a particular guest's visit and to order the appropriate preferred newspaper. In this way, a guest from Kansas City could stay informed on the daily progress of the local city football team during an autumn stay in Miami.

A more specific list of desirable improvements over the prior art follows. It is desirable and currently unavailable for a hotel to provide a mechanism for a guest to specify specific details of the guest-room environment. It is desirable for the hotel to already know the room temperature, bathroom amenities, lighting, décor and the like that a guest prefers and have the room prepared accordingly. It is also desirable for a hotel to know a guest's music and television preferences and have the appropriate media content available. An opportunity for significant resource conservation exists if only certain media content is delivered. In practice, the prior art delivers a great deal more media content to guest rooms than is consumed by the guests. The customization of other hotel amenities

such as minibar selections, laundry pick-up time, and business services is also desirable. Tracking a guest's location within the hospitality site for customizing the environment of the occupied room, such as the health club, would also be advantageous.

Wherein, can obtain the video monitoring information at scenic spot first with video monitor unit, operation management unit utilizes Visitor and the enforcement at scenic spot are managed by video information, utilize parking guidance unit that visitor's parking is carried out induction and avoid blocking up Plug, utilizes visitor's statistic unit to add up visitor, it is simple to record visitor and manage and carry out corresponding early warning And trajectory track. Wherein, described parking guidance unit specifically includes: Residue parking stall display module, described residue parking stall display module is used for showing residue parking stall quantity and position ; Input module, described input module inputs default down time and vehicle for car owner ; Selecting module, described selection module, for default down time based on user's input and vehicle, automatically selects out corresponding Parking stall ; Path planning module, described path planning module is for cooking up corresponding routing information based on the parking stall selected.

Wherein, first, residue parking stall display module is utilized can remaining parking stall number to be shown, advance notice car owner Parking space information, car owner inputs corresponding information according to oneself vehicle and down time, such as bus, stops 4 hours, at this moment select the information that module inputs according to car owner and automatically select corresponding parking stall for car owner, finally according to position, the parking stall rule selected Mark corresponding path, it is to avoid car owner can not find parking stall, it is also possible to avoid visitor disorderly stop and fight for parking stall.

Wherein, described scenic spot is carried out operation management specifically include: based on video monitoring information to visitor's uncivil behavior Carry out record, scenic spot domestic visitors is carried out early warning, source collection, visitor's motion track analysis. Wherein, described visitor's statistic unit is specifically for gathering and the analytical calculation scenic spot volume of the flow of passengers, visitor source, You Keyi Dynamic track. Wherein, described visitor's statistic unit specifically includes: Visa card, described visa card mates one by one with visitor, utilizes the usage quantity of statistics visa card can count domestic visitors, Visa card is provided with GPS locating module, radio-frequency module, current module, and GPS locating module is used for obtaining visitor and positions information, and Location information is transferred to server by communication module and obtains visitor's motion track ; Radio-frequency module is for by visitor's identity and scape District's project of playing is bound, and can use when

visitor carries out payment and opening gate ; Input module, described input module inputs visitor's source-information for visitor.

Wherein, described default down time based on user's input and vehicle, automatically select out corresponding parking stall and specifically wrap Include: parking lot is divided into long-time parking area, middle time parking area and short time parking area ; Wherein, each parking area is equipped with Large-scale parking stall, medium-sized parking stall, small-sized parking stall ; Little long-time parking area is belonged to constantly more than 24 between as when parking ; When stopping The car time little belonged to middle time parking area more than 8 hours constantly less than 24 ; Little less than 8 between as when parking belong to the short time constantly and stop Car district.

Wherein, parking lot is divided into the parking area of 3 different durations, can be good parking lot is managed, it is to avoid Blocking, and Appropriate application parking stall, be divided into the parking stall of 3 kinds of sizes can effectively utilize the area in parking lot by parking stall so that Parking quantity maximizes.

Wherein, the ratio that long-time parking area, middle time parking area are corresponding with short time parking area is: stop for a long time District: middle time parking area: short time parking area=1:2:7.

Wherein, the passenger generally going to scenic spot to play time of playing for less than 8 hours, the therefore demand of short time parking area Bigger. The one or more technical schemes provided in the embodiment of the present application, at least have the following technical effect that or advantage: Being designed as including by intelligent tourism management system owing to have employed: video monitor unit, described video monitor unit is used for Gather scenic spot and reception of visitor centered video information ; Parking guidance unit, described parking guidance unit is for entering scenic spot vehicle Row parking guidance ; Visitor's statistic unit, described visitor's statistic unit is for carrying out statistical analysis to visitor ; Operation management unit, Described operation management unit is for the statistical analysis letter of the video information gathered based on video monitor unit and visitor's statistic unit Breath, carries out the technical scheme of operation management to scenic spot, so, efficiently solve the employing of existing scenic spot management and be manually managed There is the efficiency of management relatively low, the technical problem that management effect is poor, and then achieve and automatically scenic spot is managed, the efficiency of management Higher, the preferable technique effect of management effect.

Furthermore, some user devices brought to hotels are unable to be logged in at a web-based login portal because the devices either do not include web browsing technology or do not permit the guest to access the login portal. Examples of guest devices that do not include web browsing technology include standalone teleconferencing webcam appliances, routers, Internet Protocol (IP) telephones, and other IP-enabled devices that lack a user interface capable of displaying the login portal or allowing the guest to enter the required login information. The present invention also provides a system that expands the role of traditional property-management systems to include personalizing the environment and hospitality services available to a visiting guest. The system includes a user-profile database for storing the user profile, which contains information related to a specific guest or a group of guests including guest preferences. The system also includes a data-entry component for gathering information stored in the user profile. A control module that monitors and controls the other components in the system is contained in a computer-readable medium and is responsible for decision making within the system. The control module interacts with a guest-interface component to customize a wide array of hospitality-site amenities based on information stored in the guest's user profile.

In this way, a personalized hospitality management system (STM) expands the customer service options currently available and offers solutions to common problems found in the prior art.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DIAGRAM

The present invention is described in detail below with reference to the attached drawing figures, wherein:

FIG. 1 is a block diagram depicting a general view of the major components involved in a STM; and FIG. 2 is a block diagram of a STM that depicts the components within a hospitality site in greater detail.

DESCRIPTION OF THE INVENTION

The present invention enables a property-management system to store a particular guest's likes and dislikes and use this data to create a more enjoyable visit. The property-management system now becomes a Strategic Tourism Management (STM). A STM-equipped site can share information about a particular guest with any other connected STM-equipped site. This enables the creation of a consistent, comfortable, and familiar guest experience across several hospitality sites.

A STM can control and customize many aspects of facility amenities, media offerings, and a guest's room environment. The ability to control media offerings enables more particular tracking and billing of media consumed by the guest. Furthermore, STM may originally be programmed with guest information, but it can also learn guest likes and dislikes by monitoring guest behavior.

Referring to FIGS. 1-2, the present invention is a STM **100** implemented at a hospitality site **110**. FIG. 1 is a high-level depiction of the major systems involved in a property-management system suitable for implementing the present invention. FIG. 2 is a block diagram primarily detailing the hospitality site **110** components. Hospitality site **110** is a place where a guest is hosted. Exemplary hospitality sites include, but are not limited to a hotel, motel, cruise ship, restaurant, fitness club, time-share, hospital, dormitory or any other place that offers temporary quartering facilities. As seen in FIG. 2, hospitality site **110** includes several STM components including a control module **210**, a data-entry component **212**, an administrative console **214**, a media server **216**, and one or more guest interfaces **218**. More detail on these components is provided below.

Hospitality site **110** is connected to a computer network **112**. Network **112** is preferably a wide area network (WAN), but could also be a local area network (LAN) or the Internet. Also connected to network **112** is a user-profile database **114**. User profile database **114** stores the user profiles, such as user profile X **114A**, that contain guest information. In addition to information such as billing address and activity logs, the guest information stored in a user profile includes user preferences including facility-amenity preferences, room-environment preferences, and media preferences. Depending on the nature of the hospitality site, generic preference categories vary. Examples of facility-amenity preferences include, but are not limited to, wake-up-time preferences, check-out preferences, incentive-program preferences, health-club-usage preferences, room-location preferences, facility-access preferences, minibar preferences, Internet-access preferences, telephony preferences, concierge-desk preferences, business-services preferences, parking preferences, special-assistance services preferences, and laundry preferences. Room-environment preferences include, but are not limited to home-page preferences, room-lighting preferences, décor preferences, room-temperature preferences, eating preferences, room-service preferences, convenience preferences, room-location preferences, sleeping-arrangement preferences, aroma preferences, bathroom-amenity preferences and smoking preferences. Exemplary media preferences include television-channel preferences, language preferences; genre preferences, service-duration preferences, viewing preferences, topic preferences, ratings preferences, actor preferences, style preferences, era preferences, artist preferences, protocol preferences, and format preferences.

Additional hospitality sites **116**, which are STM equipped, can access user-profile database **114** via network **112**. Guest information available to one hospitality site **110** is made available to all hospitality sites connected to network **112**.

A media content delivery system (MCDS) **118** delivers all forms of media, audio and visual, in a network-compatible format. MCDS **118** can also send other forms of data. Preferably, the media information and data are communicated as Internet Protocol (IP) packets. One skilled in the relevant art would appreciate the array of protocols that would be acceptable, not limited to a Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol (TCP/IP), a File Transfer Protocol (FTP) a Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP), and an International Telecom Union (ITU) protocol. The media information could also be sent in a proprietary protocol or any other protocol that can be used in a computer network. In addition to media content, data can also be communicated over MCDS **118**.

MCDS **118** communicates media content over network **112**. As seen in FIG. 1, MCDS **118** includes a number of media sources **120**. Media sources **120** supply media content in various forms that is transformed by other components of MCDS **118** into a network-compatible format. Many acceptable raw-media sources for providing media content exist including cable TV **120A**, a satellite feed **120B**, a Digital Versatile Disc (DVD) player **120C**, a Compact Disc (CD) player **120D**, a media player **120E**, a Video Cassette Recorder (VCR) **120F**, a TV studio **120G**, a movie studio **120H**, a production studio **120I**, and a radio program **120J**. As would be understood by one skilled in the art, any device capable of transmitting media via electrical, electronic, or electromagnetic signals is an acceptable media source **120** for the MCDS **118**.

MCDS **118** communicates information in a network-compatible format. MCDS **118** employs various types of communication-conditioning equipment **122** including a decryptor **122A**, a demodulator **122B**, and a transrater **122C**. Raw-media content from the media sources **120** can be converted into a network-compatible format using some or all of this equipment, as appropriate. Decryptor **122A** removes the encryption or “scrambling” of the incoming signal. Demodulator **122B** removes the carrier wave from the incoming signal, thus leaving only the original signal before it was modulated with a higher frequency signal in preparation for transmission. Preferably, the data is communicated in an Asynchronous Serial Interface (ASI) stream feeding into transrater **122C**. The data is conditioned and transferred in a form from demodulator **122B** that can be converted to data packets that will be communicated over a network. Transrater **122C** can receive incoming data at varying rates and transmit outgoing data at desired, selectable rates.

The data packets from transrater **122C** are communicated over a multicast network **124**. Multicast network **124** comprises multicast routers. Multicast routers are able to send data from one source to

multiple destinations. Many hospitality sites **110** and **116** receive the contents of the media packets transmitted from communication conditioning equipment **122** to multicast network **124**.

Refer now to FIG. 2, which examines hospitality site **110** in greater detail. As previously described, MCDS **118** communicates media information in a network-compatible format. This media information is communicated over network **112**. Network **112** is also connected to hospitality site **110**, control module **210**, data-entry component **212**, administrative console **214**, media server **216**, guest interface **218**, and user-profile database **114**.

Control module **210** controls and monitors the STM. The control module is the decision-making mechanism for STM. As one skilled in the relevant art would appreciate, control module **210** includes computer-readable code stored and executed in many possible ways including residing on a dedicated computer locally or remotely, residing on media server **216**, or residing on another server elsewhere in the system. Control module **210** controls the STM and makes decisions based on user-profile information located on user-profile database **114** and instructions from administrative console **214**. Control module **210** is responsible for carrying out the directives of administrative console **214**.

Data-entry component **212** is used to populate user-profile database **114**. Data-entry component **212** captures guest information and communicates it to user-profile database **114**. Data-entry component **212** contemplates guest interaction, such as a guest entering user-profile information over the Internet. Data-entry component **212** is also capable of gathering guest information without guest interaction using behavioral data collection and pattern recognition techniques. As could be appreciated by one skilled in the relevant art, data-entry component **212** includes a myriad of forms including a computer, a terminal, a kiosk, a telephony device, a television, a personal data assistant, a consumer electronics device, a speaker, a guest-monitoring application, and a default-settings programming device.

Administrative console **214** is responsible for enabling an individual with administrative authority to control and monitor all or part of the STM system depending on the individual. For example, a hotel manager may need greater control and monitoring capabilities than a hotel minibar stocker, who only needs to check guest minibar preferences and usage. Control module **210** can also be programmed through administrative console **214** if the user has the appropriate authority.

Media server **216** stores media content preferably received from MCDS **118** via network **112**. Media content may also be stored on media server **118** from many other sources including the Internet and a media player such as a DVD player or VCR. Methods of storing media on servers are

conventional in nature. Any method that accomplishes this objective is suitable for the present invention. Media is selected for storage based on the user profiles of hospitality site **110** guests. For instance, one guest may desire to watch a particular Japanese cartoon. Before or during the guest's stay, control module **210** or hotel staff negotiates with a media-content provider for the reception of the desired media selection. In a preferred embodiment, the desired media selection is received via MCDS **118**. The desired media selection is stored on media server **216** until the hotel guest requests to view the selection. In addition to storing media for guest viewing, media server **216** also dynamically stores media content, such as television channels, from MCDS **118** in a network-compatible format and then transmits the media as directed by control module **210** based on user-profile preferences. For instance, one guest may only desire to view sports channels. Another guest may only be interested in news channels.

For every guest, control module **210** distills all available media down to only the desired media based on a user profile. Only the requested media content is offered to the guest. Guests, if desired, can then peruse their media selections without wading through dozens of unwanted channels. In this way, the guest realizes a significant convenience via a system requiring less information to be transmitted than currently exists in the prior art. Control module **210** can record all media sent to a media content receiving component (MCRC) **218A**. The guest can then be billed for the media consumed. As would be appreciated by one skilled in the relevant art, control module **210** is also able to compile a list of all media consumed throughout a hospitality site for a given period of time. Guests would have the option of changing their user-profile preferences at any time to reflect changes in media preferences.

Guest interface **218** receives information and commands from other STM components and creates part of the guest-specified desired environment as stored in user-profile database **114**. Guest interface **218** is also responsible for collecting data on guest activity that is then sent to the appropriate STM component. Guest interface **218** comprises MCRC **218A** and STM controls **218B**.

MCRC **218A** receives media content in a network-compatible protocol and creates the appropriate media for the user. A preferred embodiment uses a television and a set-top device. A set-top device receives IP packets containing media information and converts the information to a National Television System Committee (NTSC) format that is transmitted to the television. The set-top device receives user input from a remote control and transmits the information to the appropriate STM component. As would be understood by one skilled in the relevant art, many other systems exist or could be designed for enabling an interactive media rendering system. Such a system could include a television, a monitor, a display device, a personal data assistant, a personal-communications system, a telephony device, a stereo, a consumer-electronics device, and a computer.

STM controls **218B** are located throughout a STM-equipped facility. STM controls **218B** are responsible for customizing the environment a particular guest experiences during their visit. STM controls **218B** receive instructions from and provide feedback to control module **210**, typically via network **112**. In addition to providing feedback on the hospitality site **110** environment, such as the temperature of a particular hot tub, the STM controls **218B** also act as points of data gathering on user activity. STM controls **218B** include controls for facility amenities, guest rooms, media transmission, and guest tracking. Facility-amenity controls customize the services offered to a guest and the environment experienced by a guest throughout hospitality site **110**. Facility-amenity controls include wake-up-time controls, check-out controls, incentive-program controls, health-club-usage controls, facility-access controls, minibar controls, Internet-access controls, telephony controls, business services controls, parking controls, special-assistance services controls, and laundry controls. Guest-room controls customize a guest's environment within a guest room. Guest-room controls include Internet-access controls, Internet-home-page controls, room-lighting controls, room-temperature controls, aroma controls, wake-up-time controls, convenience controls, and room-ventilation controls.

Media-transmission controls customize the media selections available to a guest. Media-transmission controls include television-channel controls, volume controls, language controls, service-duration controls, viewing controls, ratings controls, protocol controls, and format controls. Guest-tracking controls monitor the location of a guest throughout the managed property and send this information back to control module **210**. This information can then be used for customizing the facility-amenity and media-transmission controls located in hospitality site **110**, as appropriate. For instance, if the guest that prefers news channels and the guest that prefers sports channels happened to be working out in a hotel's health club at the same time, the media-transmission controls would alter the media transmitted in the health club accordingly.

The invention provides a kind of intelligent tourism management system, solve the employing of existing scenic spot management and be manually managed There is the efficiency of management relatively low, the technical problem that management effect is poor, it is achieved that being automatically managed scenic spot, the efficiency of management is relatively Height, the preferable technique effect of management effect. Technical scheme during the application implements is the above-mentioned technical problem of solution. General thought is as follows: Have employed and be designed as including by intelligent tourism management system: video monitor unit, described video monitor unit is used for gathering Scenic spot and reception of visitor centered video information ; Parking guidance unit, described parking guidance unit is for stopping

scenic spot vehicle Car is induced ; Visitor's statistic unit, described visitor's statistic unit is for carrying out statistical analysis to visitor ; Operation management unit,

described Operation management unit is for the video information gathered based on video monitor unit and the statistical analysis information of visitor's statistic unit, right Scenic spot carries out the technical scheme of operation management, so, efficiently solve the employing of existing scenic spot management and be manually managed existing The efficiency of management is relatively low, the technical problem that management effect is poor, and then achieves and be automatically managed scenic spot, and the efficiency of management is relatively Height, the preferable technique effect of management effect.

In order to be better understood from technique scheme, below in conjunction with Figure of description and specific embodiment to upper State technical scheme to be described in detail. FIG. 1 is a block diagram of a system for allowing a guest of a hospitality establishment to access a network service from multiple guest devices operated by the guest at the hospitality establishment according to an exemplary embodiment of the invention. In this embodiment, the hospitality establishment is a hotel and the network service is high speed Internet access (HSIA) provided to the guest devices over the hotel's computer network.

A service controller is coupled between the hotel's LAN and the Internet. The service controller in this embodiment is a computer server including a first network interface coupled to the Internet and a second network interface coupled to the hotel's LAN. The service controller further includes a module storage device and a data storage device, and each of the network interfaces and storage devices, are coupled to one or more processors. In the following description, the plural form of the word "processors" is utilized as it is common for a central processing unit (CPU) of a computer server to have multiple processors (sometimes also referred to as cores); however, it is to be understood that a single processor may also be configured to perform the below-described functionality in other implementations.

Embodiment one: In embodiment one, it is provided that a kind of intelligent tourism management system, refer to Fig. 1, described system includes: Video monitor unit, described video monitor unit is used for gathering scenic spot and reception of visitor centered video information: Parking guidance unit, described parking guidance unit is for carrying out parking guidance to scenic spot vehicle ; Visitor's statistic unit, described visitor's statistic unit is for carrying out statistical analysis to visitor ; Operation management unit, described operation management unit is for the video information gathered based on video monitor unit and

visitor's statistics The statistical analysis information of unit, carries out operation management to scenic spot.

Wherein, can obtain the video monitoring information at scenic spot first with video monitor unit, operation management unit utilizes Visitor and the enforcement at scenic spot are managed by video information, utilize parking guidance unit that visitor's parking is carried out induction and avoid blocking up Plug, utilizes visitor's statistic unit to add up visitor, it is simple to record visitor and manage and carry out corresponding early warning And trajectory track. Wherein, described parking guidance unit specifically includes: Residue parking stall display module, described residue parking stall display module is used for showing residue parking stall quantity and position ;

Input module, described input module inputs default down time and vehicle for car owner ; Selecting module, described selection module, for default down time based on user's input and vehicle, automatically selects out corresponding Parking stall ; Path planning module, described path planning module is for cooking up corresponding routing information based on the parking stall selected.

Wherein, first, residue parking stall display module is utilized can remaining parking stall number to be shown, advance notice car owner Parking space information, car owner inputs corresponding information according to oneself vehicle and down time, such as bus, stops 4 hours, at this moment select Select the information that module inputs according to car owner and automatically select corresponding parking stall for car owner, finally according to position, the parking stall rule selected Mark corresponding path, it is to avoid car owner cannot find parking stall, it is also possible to avoid visitor disorderly stop and fight for parking stall.

Wherein, described scenic spot is carried out operation management specifically include: based on video monitoring information to visitor's uncivil behavior Carry out record, scenic spot domestic visitors is carried out early warning, source collection, visitor's motion track analysis. Wherein, described visitor's statistic unit is specifically for gathering and the analytical calculation scenic spot volume of the flow of passengers, visitor source, You Keyi Dynamic track.

Wherein, described visitor's statistic unit specifically includes:

Visa card, described visa card mates one by one with visitor, utilizes the usage quantity of statistics visa card can count domestic visitors, Visa card is provided with GPS locating module, radio-frequency module, current module, and GPS locating module is used for obtaining visitor and positions information, and Location information is transferred to server by communication module and obtains visitor's motion track ; Radio-frequency module is for by visitor's identity and scape

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Wherein, the passenger generally going to scenic spot to play time of playing for less than 8 hours, the therefore demand of short time parking area Bigger. Technical scheme in above-mentioned the embodiment of the present application, at least has the following technical effect that or advantage: Being designed as including by intelligent tourism management system owing to have employed: video monitor unit, described video monitor unit is used for Gather scenic spot and reception of visitor centered video information ; Parking guidance unit, described parking guidance unit is for entering scenic spot vehicle Row parking guidance ; Visitor's statistic unit, described visitor's statistic unit is for carrying out statistical analysis to visitor ; Operation management unit, Described operation management unit is for the statistical analysis letter of the video information gathered based on video monitor unit and visitor's statistic unit Breath, carries out the technical scheme of operation management to scenic spot, so, efficiently solve the employing of existing scenic spot management and be manually managed There is the efficiency of management relatively low, the technical problem that management effect is poor, and then achieve and automatically scenic spot is managed, the efficiency of management Higher, the preferable technique effect of management effect.

Although preferred embodiments of the present invention have been described, but those skilled in the art once know basic creation Property concept, then can make other change and amendment to these embodiments. So, claims are intended to be construed to include excellent Select embodiment and fall into all changes and the amendment of the scope of the invention. Obviously, those skilled in the art can carry out various change and the modification essence without deviating from the present invention to the present invention God and scope. So, if these amendments of the present invention and modification belong to the scope of the claims in the present invention and equivalent technologies thereof Within, then the present invention is also intended to comprise these change and modification.

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